

The Role of Strategic Agility in Developing Radical Innovation

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ABSTRACT:

It is the objective of this research to determine the contribution of strategic agility in the radical innovation of the General Company for Electrical and Electronic Industries in Baghdad. The research problem revolves around the concept and dimensions of strategic agility as a facilitatory agent for remarkable radical innovation. To meet the research objectives, we employed descriptive-analytical methodology which includes questionnaires on the research variables of the employees from the General Company for Electrical and Electronic Industries in Baghdad which included 75 employees in a sample. Data were analyzed statistically using several statistical methods: arithmetic mean, standard deviation, Pearson correlation coefficient, statistical software (SPSS.V.29) and (Amos.V.29). Results showed an association of the variables with the study variables in correlation and impact.

Keywords: Strategic agility, Radical innovation.

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INTRODUCTION

In today's business environment of fierce competition, industrial companies face ever-increasing challenges because of rapid technological advancements, market pressures, and evolving customer demands. These pressures need the company to keep current with managerial and strategic practices if it is to achieve lasting development. Strategic agility has emerged as a major dynamic capability. It empowers organizations to efficiently respond to continuous change. Simultaneously, radical creativity has morphed into one of the main pillars of sustainable success. This is where these two concepts go hand-in-hand, in the crucial intersection where organizations can easily adjust to quickly changing contexts and design novel, unorthodox solutions to gain competitive edge in dynamic markets.

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RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Problem

The key research question of the current study aims to explore and explain the relationship between strategic agility and radical creativity:

What is the role of strategic agility in enhancing radical creativity among the employees of the General Company for Electrical and Electronic Industries / Baghdad?

The following sub-questions derive from this central question:

1. Do the employees of the General Company for Electrical and Electronic Industries / Baghdad have a clear vision of the nature and dimensions of strategic agility?
2. To what extent do the employees of the General Company for Electrical and Electronic Industries / Baghdad perceive the importance of radical creativity?
3. What is the nature of the relationship and impact between strategic agility and radical creativity?

Research Significance

The significance of this study lies in its contribution to achieving the following objectives:

1. The study is important as it highlights the role of strategic agility in linking organizations to external developments, viewing it as a means to anticipate changes, exploit available opportunities, and avoid threats and risks.
2. It contributes to providing new information in the field of strategic agility and radical creativity based on the conclusions and recommendations the study will yield.
3. The current research contributes to offering new insights into strategic agility and radical creativity through the findings and recommendations that will be reached.

Research Objectives

1. To assess the extent to which strategic agility contributes to enhancing radical creativity, and to provide a new conceptual framework related to this contemporary topic.
2. To identify the levels of strategic agility by revealing the extent to which its dimensions are present among the employees of the General Company for Electrical and Electronic Industries / Baghdad.
3. To measure and evaluate radical creativity and verify whether the research sample possesses high levels of radical creativity.
4. To determine the level of impact of strategic agility legacy on radical creativity from the perspective of the study sample.

Hypothetical Framework of the Study

In light of the previously discussed elements, the hypothetical framework of the study is illustrated in Figure (1):

- **Independent Variable:** Strategic Agility, which is measured through three dimensions: *strategic sensitivity*, *leadership unity*, and *resource fluidity*, based on the scale developed by [1].
- **Dependent Variable:** Radical Creativity, represented as a unidimensional variable consisting of eight items, measured based on the scale by [2]

Research Hypotheses

Main Hypothesis (1H): There is a statistically significant correlation between strategic agility and radical creativity. This main hypothesis branches into the following sub-hypotheses:

- a. There is a statistically significant correlation between strategic sensitivity and radical creativity.
- b. There is a statistically significant correlation between leadership unity and radical creativity.

c. There is a statistically significant correlation between resource fluidity and radical creativity.

Underlying Hypothesis (2H): Strategic agility exerts a statistically significant effect on radical creativity.

This hypothesis subdivides into the subsequent sub-hypotheses:

a. There is a statistically significant impact of strategic sensitivity on radical creativity.

b. Leadership unity has a statistically significant effect on radical creativity.

c. Resource fluidity has an impact on radical creativity that is statistically significant.

Figure 1. The Hypothetical Model of the Study

THE THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

The Concept of Strategic Agility

Strategic agility originated early on in literature associated with flexible manufacturing systems and as such tends in practice to be treated as a synonym for flexibility. Their relationship is not dissimilar to capability versus efficiency [3]. Strategic agility is described as the ability of an organization to rewire itself and continue flexibility without loss of efficiency. Three core capabilities important to strategic agility have been identified by researchers: strategic sensitivity, resource fluidity, and collective commitment [4]. This includes decisions businesses make in response to turbulent settings (in contrast to routine changes that affect only the strategic base of the organization and require a continuous process of systemic change). The three capabilities—strategic sensitivity, resource fluidity, and collective commitment—are core to fostering agility and responsiveness in a business environment with fluctuations [5].

According to [6], strategic agility can be categorized into three patterns:

1. **Agility for stability**, aimed at coping with crises or disruptions that could be harmful. These patterns involve a low degree of change.
2. **Agility for variety**, designed to vary degrees of change and present a fluctuating change pattern.
3. **Agility for transformation**, aimed at maintaining or increasing the organization's flexibility for continuous transformation, involving high degrees of change.

Strategic agility is a recent term in theory based on the concept of strategic change and renewal stressing flexible, transformational organizations and adaptive agility in face of environmental or external uncertainty or disruption while seizing new opportunities [7]. Timing of decisions, the implementation of business strategies or actions, following up to environmental changes or prior models for agility, in the early and rapid, are some of its components [8]. According to [9], strategic agility implies resource allocation to build and deploy critical capabilities, and the dynamic balance of such capabilities over time to facilitate flexibility.

It allows organizations to pivot quickly without losing momentum, boosting resilience in turbulent settings. [10] identify it as one of the key success factors that opens the road towards continuous adjustment and re-alignment of strategies to drive innovation and value creation; a process driven

by dynamic capabilities, such as resource fluidity, strategic sensitivity, and collective commitment. Academic consensus, in spite of a disparate definition, is focused on specific core attributes: speed of response, quick adaptation and the capacity to tackle new challenges or change [11]. Strategic agility is a higher-order management approach in the aggregate, as it reflects leadership capacity to anticipate, adapt to, and innovate in the face of unforeseen challenges — turning challenges into opportunities for organization-wide success [12].

Characteristics of Strategic Agility

[13] indicated some important features of strategic agility as follows over the last 20 years:

1. Strategic agility involves a set of actions taken by an organization operating in an environment characterized by rapid and unpredictable change.
2. Strategic agility requires changes that are distinct from typical or routine types of change
3. Speed is essential in sensing environmental changes and responding appropriately. Therefore, strategic agility demands significant investment in resources to maintain high levels of flexibility and responsiveness.
4. The adoption of modular structures, these capabilities, central to strategic agility, lead to changes in the nature of technological work, the types of knowledge assets generated, the ways learning occurs at both individual and organizational levels, and the characteristics of the organization's human resources.

Determinants of Strategic Agility

Strategic agility is classified according to a cluster of essential determinants, which include planning, organization, people, and technology [14]:

1. **Planning:** A detailed and pragmatic planning that aims to achieve three key goals simultaneously (objectives, resources, and time) and to do so in an efficient way through the effective use of resources and in the shortest time. This means planning is a process of forecasting future events and preparing for them in advance.
2. **Organization:** Organization is the process of combining human and material resources through a formal system with defined roles, responsibilities, and authority. This is necessary for reaching targets, enabling operational functions, and for encouraging employee collaboration on common tasks. So, the most important thing about performance is that all the pieces work, and a failure can take away from the overall success of the entire company.
3. **People:** This will allude to the extent to which the organization builds elements of surprise, employs employee knowledge, and adds capabilities to cope with market dynamics.

The Importance of Strategic Agility

Organizational excellence, survival and sustainability depend upon strategic agility. Strategic agility is required because of the constant shifts happening both within the external environment and the internal work environment. We can summarize the importance of strategic agility as follows [15]:

1. Strategic agility is a fundamental requirement for the survival and continued success of organizations.
2. It emphasizes strategic thinking and strategic vision.
3. Strategic agility serves as a key to success in dynamic business environments.
4. The presence of agility within organizations is a critical tool for managing unexpected changes and mitigating risks posed by competing organizations.
5. Strategic agility equips the organization with the ability to respond rapidly to external environmental changes, anticipate future developments, and adapt accordingly.
6. It reflects the organization's capacity to manage and control continuous change effectively.

Objectives of Strategic Agility

In short, the main goal of organizational agility is to ensure the organization's survival and continuity in a competitive business environment and to be able to adjust effectively to changes in the work environment and to benefit from available opportunities. Four characteristics of agile organizations have been widely recognized; these are flexibility, efficiency, responsiveness, and accountability. Strategic agility goals for more data-based objectives are also described below [16]:

1. Ensuring the organization's continuity, stability, and survival in a context of an increasingly difficult environment.
2. Empowers and prepares the organization to mobilize and direct resources that can be used to exploit strategic opportunities via situation analysis, goal setting, strategic planning, and monitoring implementation.
3. Implementing a crisis management model based on transformational change of the activities and supporting innovations that can be adopted by the organization as part of leading transformation.

Strategic agility aims at institutions of higher education across the role spectrum, covering expansion, creative transformation, mobilizing sustainable technology, and continuous radical improvement.

Dimensions of Strategic Agility

The dimensions of strategic agility, however novel, have not been consistently identified due to the dynamic and evolving nature of these dimensions; researchers and scholars alike have given different terms and the number of dimensions. This research adopts the following dimensions [17]:

1. **Strategic Sensitivity:** Strategic sensitivity is the capacity by an organization to recognize and react to internal and external shifts that may affect its strategic direction. This requires foresight and awareness to recognize emerging opportunities and threats; it promotes speedy and proactive action — often before competitors and stakeholders. This capacity is reinforced by strategic foresight (predicting trends) and strategic insight (analyzing the environment) to guide effective decision-making [17].
2. **Collective Commitment:** This concept refers to a shared commitment and mutual understanding among members of an organization. It has been described as “a common ground of shared interests, empathy, and trust among organizational members to enhance their participation and positive interaction.” Others have defined it as “a shared mindset and collective psychological state among a defined group of individuals regarding their employer, characterized by feelings of loyalty and the willingness to invest mental and physical energy in helping the organization achieve its goals” [18].
3. **Resource Fluidity:** Resource fluidity is the internal ability of an organization to reconfigure competencies and quickly reallocate resources as needed to address new strategic directions. It involves aligning strategy with organizational structure through flexible business models, systems, and modular architectures that can be rapidly adjusted [19].

This capability is vital for strategic agility, as strategic sensitivity and collective commitment alone are not enough. Resources must be accessible through diverse channels, rather than being fixed, so managers can obtain what they need when needed. Effective planning should decouple business outcomes from resource ownership, ensuring availability while recognizing that some resources are harder to mobilize than others [17].

The Concept of Innovation

Innovation is a multi-stage process where organizations convert ideas into new or enhanced products, services, or processes to drive progress, gain competition, and stand out in the market. It typically falls into two categories: incremental (gradual improvements) and radical (disruptive, breakthrough changes) [20].

The general definition of innovation according to the **Oslo Manual**, which applies across all economic sectors, is:

“Innovation is a new or improved product or process (or a combination thereof) that differs significantly from previous products or processes of the unit and has been made available to potential users or introduced into operation by the organization” [21].

Additionally, [22] defined innovation as both invention and exploitation. That is, innovation as a term refers to both marketable novel ideas and ideas that have already been successfully commercialized [23].

The innovation process consists of four interrelated stages, although they function across different timeframes, strategies, and roadmaps. These four stages are [24]:

1. Idea generation regarding products, technologies, processes, or the organization itself.
2. Research or technology management.
3. Management or planning of product lines or programs.
4. Management of new product development projects, which deliver new offerings to the market and contribute fundamentally to value creation for the organization.

Types of Creativity

[25] summarized the types of creativity as follows:

1. **Incremental Creativity:** Incremental creativity involves small changes that build upon existing knowledge and experience.
2. **Modular Creativity:** Modular creativity requires significant changes in the design concept of a system or a department within an organization.
3. **Architectural Creativity:** Architectural creativity involves minor changes within one of the components or departments of the organization.
4. **Systemic Creativity:** Systemic creativity is defined by its integration with several independent innovations that must work together to perform new functions or enhance the overall performance of the organization.
5. **Radical Creativity:** Radical creativity represents breakthroughs in science or technology that often change the nature of an industry.

Concept of Radical Creativity

Radical creativity forms a prominent element of creativity management, related to the development process and the roles played by the research and development departments. It usually generates disruptive innovations that confront the status quo [26] and are revolutionary technological transformations beyond current practices [27]. More recent research suggests that radical creativity consists of leveraging organizational knowledge in new contexts, with customer needs and performance metrics being critical criteria for selection [28].

It is systemic and complex transformation within organizations that is driven by new knowledge elements and relies on internal and external collaboration [29]. In contrast to incremental improvement, radical creativity is directed at new opportunities and serves to drive new technological trajectories [30], often requiring a transition from customer-centric to design-oriented ones [31].

Radical creativity is costly [32] and also risky because of its dependence on research and development (R&D) but remains essential for organizational success and innovation [33]. This results in disruptive products and processes, unlike incremental innovation, that targets small improvements [34]. An example here is the self-driving car, as radical innovation combines hitherto unrelated knowledge in conditions of uncertainty [35], emphasizing its centrality in economic progress and transformation [36].

Types of Radical Creativity

Products, processes, and organizational creativity are identified as the three main types of creativity [37]. Below is a brief explanation of these types:

1. **Product Creativity:** Product creativity involves the marketing of a significantly improved or entirely new product or service. It is the result of new knowledge or technologies (including information and communication technologies) [37].
2. **Process Creativity:** Process creativity refers to the innovative application or combination of existing knowledge and technologies across organizational functions like sales, production, and delivery. It can also arise from new knowledge or technological advancements, particularly in ICT, or through creative reuse of existing resources [37].
3. **Organizational Creativity:** Organizational creativity involves creating new or significantly improved methods, systems, or business practices. It stems from new knowledge or technologies, including ICTs, or from innovative uses and combinations of existing resources [37].

Characteristics of Radical Creativity

The characteristics of radical creativity are as follows [38]:

1. It is based on science and is closely related to the evolution of current sciences.
2. It is driven by the ability to develop new technologies, the capability to apply them, and the response to the changes they bring about.
3. It addresses problems that cannot be solved in a short time using existing technologies.
4. Radical innovations often disrupt or transform existing technologies, business models, markets, and societies.

Importance of Radical Creativity

1. Creativity is one of the main drivers of competitive success which, through radical innovation, generates competitive gain [25,39] and transforms and makes market change, economic growth and sectoral differentiation a driving variable. They depend on creativity for the agility of an organization to adjust to changing environments, technological developments, technological changes and market environments [39]. As a result, organizations employ innovation to stay ahead of the competition, so creativity is crucial for the success of organizations. It is in the future the business world as well, because business can achieve competitive advantage through rapid, disruptive innovations and new market trends. Richer firms can sustain long-term viability and a good position to compete through disruptive innovation and create value for customers with radical creativity [40]. Introduce and implement new ideas.

2. Introduce and implement new ideas.
3. Deliver new services.
4. Develop new processes.
5. Develop new technologies.
6. Redesign new organizational structures.
7. Develop strategies and programs to improve performance and sustainability.

Stages of Radical Creativity

[41-44] defined the stages of radical innovation as follows:

1. **Preparation or Readiness Stage:** In this stage, the problem is identified and examined from all angles. This involves gathering relevant information, skills, and experiences through memory and readings. The information is then categorized by connecting the elements of the problem, which is known as the preparation stage.
2. **Incubation Stage:** This stage is characterized by a period of waiting and hesitation, during which the mind is freed from distractions and irrelevant ideas. It is a time of deep and continuous reflection on the problem.
3. **Illumination Stage:** In this stage, the spark of innovation occurs, and the new idea that leads to solving the problem is generated.

4. **Verification Stage:** This is the final stage of the creative process, where the innovator tests the idea, reconsiders it, experiments with the solution, and verifies its success.

PRACTICAL ASPECT OF THE RESEARCH

Descriptive Statistics of the Research Variables

A. Strategic Agility Variable: The strategic agility variable consists of three dimensions, which are:

1. **Strategic Sensitivity:** Table 3 presents the mean values, standard deviation, and the significance of each item for the strategic sensitivity dimension:

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics Distribution for the Strategic Sensitivity Dimension

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
X1	4.29	.892	86%	2
X2	4.13	.969	84%	3
X3	4.31	.856	87%	1
Total Dimension of Strategic Sensitivity	4.28	.858	86%	

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of the SPSS program version 29.

2. The dimension of Strategic Sensitivity showed high importance (86%), as suggested by the mean 4.28 and the standard deviation of 0.858, indicating a strong agreed value between the members on the importance of this variable for the strategic planning of an organisation. The low standard deviation has validated the accuracy of the responses. Leadership Unity Table 4 shows the mean, standard deviation, and the significance of items in the leadership unity dimension:

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics Distribution for the Leadership Unity Dimension

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
X1	4.35	.907	%87	2
X2	4.27	.914	%85	3
X3	4.39	.837	%88	1
Total dimension of leadership unity	4.31	.877	%86	

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of the SPSS program version 29.

3. The Leadership Unity dimension also gained an overall 86% significance, with a mean value of 4.31 and standard deviation of 0.877, wherein participants indicated a very high level of agreement with and consistency in their sense of values for all items. A lower level of dispersion strengthens the findings by assuring the reliability and stability of the results.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics Distribution for the Resource Fluidity Dimension

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
X1	4.25	.967	%84	3
X2	4.17	1.06	%83	1
X3	4.33	.936	%86	2
Total resource fluidity dimension	4.28	.975	%84	

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of the SPSS program version 29.

For the Resource Fluidity dimension, the mean score was 4.28, which denotes that participants agreed with the importance and effectiveness of resource fluidity within the organization. A standard

deviation of 0.975 indicates a limited deviation in opinions; however, across the board it indicates consensus with stable and consistent views. With a relative importance of 84%, participants consider Resource Fluidity highly crucial to organizational success, and respondents' reliability and homogeneity of results is evidenced by the low variability in responses.

Summary of the Strategic Agility Variable

The results of the study also show that the respondents tend to strongly agree that Strategic Agility is important when it comes to organizations as evidenced by a high mean score (4.29) and low standard deviation (0.373), thus indicating the consensus. With a relative importance of 85%, Strategic Agility is seen as crucial for enhancing organizational performance, and the low variability in responses confirms the reliability and stability of these findings.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics Distribution for the Strategic Agility Variable

		Mean	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking	
1	Total resource fluidity dimension	4.28	.975	%84	Strongly Agree	3
2	Total dimension of leadership unity	4.31	.877	%86	Strongly Agree	1
3	Total dimension of strategic sensitivity	4.28	.858	86%	Strongly Agree	2
Total Strategic Agility Variable		4.31	.375	%85	Strongly Agree	

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of the SPSS program version 29.

B. Radical Creativity Variable: The **Radical Creativity** variable is unidimensional.

Table 7 below shows the mean values, standard deviation, and the significance of each item related to the **Radical Creativity** variable:

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics Distribution for the Radical Creativity Variable

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
X1	3.90	0.820	74%	3
X2	3.84	0.848	73%	4
X3	4.03	0.734	79%	1
X4	3.94	0.814	76%	2
X5	3.88	0.860	71%	6
X6	3.77	0.879	69%	7
X7	3.89	0.850	73%	5
X8	3.79	0.877	68%	8
Total radical Innovation variable	3.92	0.819	72%	

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of the SPSS program version 29.

Overall results show a strong level of agreement among participants regarding the significance of Radical Creativity with a mean value (3.61) implying a good amount of agreement. That the standard deviation is 0.809 indicates that there is some variation in opinions, adding confidence to the results. The relative importance (72%) indicates that the participants understand the importance of Radical Creativity for improving Strategic Agility. The results indicate common ground among the participants on the importance of the different items in the Radical Creativity variable. The relatively low standard deviations add further weight to the findings and confirm the consistency of views on the importance of Radical Creativity for achieving organizational performance.

Hypothesis Testing

Second Main Hypothesis:

This hypothesis posits (There is a statistically significant correlation between Strategic Agility and Radical Creativity). Table 8 shows a strong positive statistically significant correlation between Strategic Agility and Radical Creativity of (0.4590). From this main hypothesis, the following sub-hypotheses emerge:

First Sub-Hypothesis:

This hypothesis suggests (There is a statistically significant correlation between Strategic Sensitivity and Radical Creativity). Table 8 indicates a statistically significant correlation between the Strategic Sensitivity dimension and Radical Creativity, with a correlation value of (0.4260), representing a moderate positive relationship.

Second Sub-Hypothesis:

This hypothesis suggests (There is a statistically significant correlation between Leadership Unity and Radical Creativity). Table 8 shows a statistically significant correlation between the Leadership Unity dimension and Radical Creativity, with a correlation value of (0.3850), indicating a moderate positive relationship.

Third Sub-Hypothesis:

This hypothesis suggests (There is a statistically significant correlation between Resource Fluidity and Radical Creativity). Table 8 presents a statistically significant correlation between the Resource Fluidity dimension and Radical Creativity, with a value of (0.4910), showing a moderate positive relationship. Based on the above, the first main hypothesis can be accepted, which asserts (There is a statistically significant correlation between Strategic Agility and its dimensions and Radical Creativity).

Table 8. Correlation Values between Strategic Agility and Radical Innovation

Independent variable	Strategic Agility	Dimensions of Strategic Agility		
		Resource Fluidity	Leadership Unity	Strategic Sensitivity
Dependent variable				
Radical Innovation	.4590	.4260	.3850	.4910
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.002	.001	.000
Decision (Result)	There is a strong positive and statistically significant correlation at the 0.01 significance level between strategic agility and its dimensions and radical innovation.			
. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the SPSS.V.29 program.

Main Hypothesis Three: There is a statistically significant effect of strategic agility on radical innovation.

Table 9 shows that as customers perceive the importance of the quality of their experiences, it leads to an increase in their job performance. In other words, increasing strategic agility by one standard unit leads to an improvement in radical innovation by (0.352) with a standard error of (0.65).

Table 9. Final Results of the Effect of Strategic Agility on Radical Innovation.

Sig.	R ² Value	Critical Value	Standard Error	Standard Estimate	Path		
0.001	0.297	0.65	0.71	0.352	Radical Innovation	---	Strategic Agility

Figure 2. The Structural Model for the Effect of Strategic Agility on Radical Innovation
Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the outputs of AMOS.V.29.

The strategic agility variable contributed to explaining (0.297) of the variance in radical innovation, while the remaining value is attributed to variables outside the scope of the study.

From the main hypothesis, the following sub-hypotheses arise:

Sub-Hypothesis One: The hypothesis suggests that there is a statistically significant effect of strategic sensitivity on radical innovation. Table 10 shows that as employees perceive the importance of the strategic sensitivity dimension, it leads to an improvement in radical innovation. In other words, increasing the strategic sensitivity dimension by one standard unit results in an improvement in radical innovation by (0.272) with a standard error of (0.066).

Sub-Hypothesis Two: The hypothesis is that the leadership unity leads to radical innovation with a statistically significant effect. As seen in Table 10, whenever organizations recognize the importance of the leadership unity dimension, it leads to an improvement in radical innovation in the studied organizations. Put differently, the increase in the leadership unity dimension by one standard unit corresponds to a radical innovation increase by (0.289) with a standard error of (0.064).

Sub-Hypothesis Three: The hypothesis suggests that there is a statistically significant effect of resource fluidity on radical innovation. Table 10 shows the significant effect of resource fluidity on radical innovation, meaning employees recognize the importance of factors that affect the speed, accuracy, and ease with which the user can obtain the required service, and the necessity for organizations to improve these factors. In other words, increasing the resource fluidity dimension by one standard unit results in an improvement in radical innovation by (0.241) with a standard error of (0.022).

Based on the above results, the main hypothesis three can be accepted: There is a statistically significant direct effect of strategic agility on radical innovation, meaning that employees surveyed recognize the need to focus on these variables.

Table 10. Direct Effect Results of Strategic Agility Dimensions on Radical Innovation

Sig.	R ² Value	Critical Value	Standard Error	Standard Estimate	Path		
0.001	.3440	2.812	0.066	0.272	Radical Innovation	--	Resource Fluidity
0.002		.1035	0.064	0.289	Radical Innovation	--	Leadership Unity
0.876		1.014	0.022	0.241	Radical Innovation	--	Strategic Sensitivity

Figure 3. The Structural Model for the Effect of Strategic Agility Dimensions on Radical Innovation

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the outputs of AMOS.V.29.

CONCLUSIONS

The research results revealed a statistically significant correlation between strategic agility and radical innovation, indicating that adopting strategic agility practices effectively contributes to achieving radical innovation within the company.

It was found that the dimensions of strategic agility (strategic sensitivity, collective commitment, and resource fluidity) are effective drivers of radical innovation, as they contribute to generating unconventional solutions and enhancing creativity.

The results demonstrated a direct effect of strategic agility on radical innovation, reflecting the importance of formulating flexible strategies that respond to environmental changes.

The findings highlighted variations in the level of employee awareness of strategic agility concepts, indicating the need to enhance institutional understanding of these concepts to support their effective implementation.

The research revealed that investing in the development of strategic agility within the company is a key lever for generating radical creative ideas, especially in a dynamic and complex industrial environment like the one observed in the company under study.

RECOMMENDATIONS

A clear strategy in order for a company to improve strategic agility through redesign of processes at all levels of management must be taken. This will be possible through reconfiguring the company's operations and organizational structures in line with today's complex, fast emerging industrial environment.

The implementation of specialized training programs and workshops that will enhance the level of strategic awareness should enable employees to understand and apply the concept of strategic agility.

A culture of innovation and creativity will thrive in the organization by creating an organizational environment that encourages experimenting with new ideas without the fear of failure.

We need to augment the use of environmental analysis tools and predictions of changes as a part of the expansion of agile strategic vision, which enables quick and effective responses to opportunities and threats.

As a result, suggestions include encouraging top management to support radical creative initiatives through flexible decision-making and delegation of authority, thereby enabling employees to contribute to improvement and innovation.

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